

A Review of Forage and Seed Yield and Quality Related Traits in Sainfoin (*Onobrychis* spp.)

Ebrar Karabulut Uzun^{1*}

¹Adana Alparslan Türkeş Science and Technology University, Adana, Türkiye, 01250

²The Land Institute, Salina, Kansas, USA, 67401

*Corresponding: ebrarkarabulut95@gmail.com

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Abstract

Sainfoin (*Onobrychis* spp.) is an important forage legume that has been cultivated in temperate regions of the northern hemisphere for centuries. Besides its potential to provide required protein to livestock through nutritional superiorities, sainfoin provides ecosystem services via reducing the enteric methane release from ruminants (reducing greenhouse gas emissions in the animal production systems), synthetic nitrogen dependency through biological nitrogen fixation, and erosion with perennial and strong root systems. In addition to all these attributes, sainfoin has recently been selected as an alternative perennial pulse crop and is currently under domestication. Success in breeding pulse crops or utilizing them as a dual-use grain and forage would require the effective evaluation of yield and quality properties of genetic resources. This review aims to compile information on sainfoin seed and forage yield potential, as well as quality parameters, through an evaluation of previous literature.

Keywords: Sainfoin, *Onobrychis* spp., forage, seed, yield, quality

Introduction

Animal based protein is of great importance for humans to have a balanced, adequate, and healthy diet.¹ Feed sources drive total animal production costs and significantly affect the profitability of the enterprise as well as widespread availability of the animal-based protein. For this reason, forages are crucial as they are inexpensive, accessible, and positively affect the digestive activities of ruminant animals.^{2,3} Turkish forage and feed production generally fails to meet the demand despite meadows and pastures being widely used in the country.⁴ To meet the forage and protein demand of the animal feed industry through domestic production, forage crop species and methods need to be reevaluated in Türkiye. Specifically, new forage crop species and varieties should be developed that can adapt to different ecological regions and provide efficient and high-quality forage. Sainfoin is one of the prominent forages that could provide necessary protein to farm animals.⁵⁻⁷

Sainfoin (*Onobrychis* spp.) is a perennial legume grown in different ecological conditions and several species are domesticated as sainfoin including *Onobrychis viciifolia* Scop., *Onobrychis transcaucasica* Grossh., *Onobrychis altissima* Grossh., and *Onobrychis arenaria* (Kit.) DC and all are naturally distributed around Anatolia, Caucasus region and Iran.⁸⁻¹⁰ Sainfoin is largely cultivated to the temperate regions of the northern hemisphere^{11,12} but the cultivation in Türkiye is mostly concentrated in Eastern and Central Anatolia.^{2,13,14}

Sainfoin has several advantages compared to other fo-

rages including preventing bloating and limiting methane and ammonia emissions from cattle.¹⁵⁻¹⁷ Recently, sainfoin has been suggested as a perennial pulse crop candidate and being under domestication for human consumption. Sainfoin seeds are being evaluated as perennial pulse under the name Baki Bean™.¹⁸

Sainfoin germplasm show great variation in terms of winter hardiness, maturity, yield potential. Nonetheless, research on sainfoin has been rather limited and the existing variation and potential is largely unexplored.¹⁹ The studies targeting genetic information of the crop and wild relatives are relatively limited. Improvement of sainfoin as forage or as a pulse crop require coordinated efforts for evaluation of a broad-based germplasm across all the cultivated species along with a thorough genomic evaluation of the available germplasm. Particularly, seed yield potential of a broad range of available germplasm could help to understand the degree of variation and identify germplasm that has high potential for seed yield and nutrition composition. Nonetheless, seed yield related traits are rather cumbersome to measure accurately. Utilization of the state-of-art techniques such as image analyses along with the artificial intelligence (AI) can help precisely estimate these difficult traits in many genotypes and accessions.

The current paper is an attempt to systematically review yield and seed yield related literature of sainfoin and identify the potential research venues for such an important and promising crop.

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Sainfoin as a valuable fodder crop

Sainfoin is noted to be a suitable forage legume for the barren and calcareous soils.^{2,13,14,20} The species prefers well-drained soils and does not grow well in heavy soils or stagnant water encountered under flood irrigation.^{21,22} Sainfoin can be planted as a monoculture but is often mixed with grass or alfalfa.^{23,24}

Recent studies have shown that sainfoin has anthelmintic properties and the ability to protect protein against premature spoilage in the rumen when used as a forage crop in ruminant diets which could be attributed to the tannin composition of the sainfoin in the leaf.^{25–29} Sainfoin fodder is rich in potassium, calcium, magnesium, phosphorus, zinc, and iron minerals, especially in the stem elongation stage.^{22,30} In addition, sainfoin is rich in secondary metabolites, which are beneficial compounds. These secondary metabolites are concentrated in various parts of the sainfoin and are known to benefit animal and human health.^{22,30,31} Cultivated sainfoin varieties are very important and tasty for ruminants and have a crude protein content.^{22,23,32} Proximate nutritional quality parameters of sainfoin have been found to exceed all standard values recommended for ruminant animals.³³ Sainfoin starts vegetatively in early spring and remains green throughout the summer.^{22,34} Because the sainfoin grows upright and the first-cut hay yield of the sainfoin is generally higher than that of clover, it is preferred for haying; however, later dry matter (DM) yield is mostly equal in new cultivars or 20% to 30% less than alfalfa in old sainfoin cultivars. Therefore, sainfoin can be considered a short-lived forage crop and adapted for early-season harvest or grazing.^{16,23}

In addition to being an excellent feed source, sainfoin can fulfil ecological services. For instance, sainfoins are known to be a good source of nectar and pollen for many pollinator species such as honeybees, bumblebees, solitary bees, and other insects.^{26,35,36}

Major morphological traits

There are several agronomic traits studied and reported in sainfoin. One of the important traits in sainfoin is the plant height and the earlier reports indicate a wide variation among species and accessions. For instance, *O. transcucasica* reported to have a plant height of 60 cm whereas *O. altissima* reaches 90 cm.³⁷ Generally, a variation of 30-90 cm in height has been reported.³⁸ The sainfoin has fleshy and hollow erect stems. As perennial plants have well developed root systems, sainfoin roots are thick, deep, and branched roots with many thin lateral roots.²⁶ The depth of the taproot system is reported to reach up to three meters.³⁸

When considered as a temperate forage legume, the leaves contain a high protein content for livestock. The compound sainfoin leaves alternate on the stem and consist of 11-29 leaflets that are narrow at the apex and broad at the base, with a single terminal leaflet at the apex and pairing the entire leaf except for a single terminal leaflet at the tip.²⁶

The sainfoin flower heads have about 80 rosy-pink flowers attached to short stems that connect them to the main stem.^{22,26,39} The sainfoin flowers have a purple, pink, whitish or yellowish color and the flowers are col-

lected in auxiliary racemes or spikes.³⁸ The flowers in the panicle open from the bottom up.⁴⁰ The fruit is a semi-circular, small flat pod with a single seed. The fruit coat surrounds the seed. The semicircular edge of the fruit is thorny. Sainfoin seeds are bean-shaped and dark brown with 1000-grain seeds weight of 17-32 g.⁴⁰

Forage yield and quality traits

Numerous studies have been conducted to investigate the yield and quality characteristics of sainfoin (*Onobrychis sativa* L.), with the aim of identifying germplasm with higher dry matter yield and improved forage quality.^{33,41,42} The elevated condensed tannin (CT) content in sainfoin make it an important forage capable of preventing bloating in ruminants, for reducing methane release from dairy production systems, and for increasing the feed quality and digestibility. CT concentrations were measured in Communis and Bifera accessions in a study that tested whether accession and environment affected CT structures in the sainfoin. It was concluded that CTs in Bifera accessions have more stable and predictable properties, confirming their role in reducing bloat and methane emissions.⁴³ Nonetheless, a set of controlled studies specifically testing the methane release from different sainfoin feed ration as well as different sainfoin accession will provide a more solid conclusion about the potential of sainfoin for reducing greenhouse gas emissions and fulfilling the ecosystem services while increasing animal performance.

A study was conducted to observe the effects of different harvesting times on the raw nutrient content, tannin levels, and digestibility of dehydrated sainfoin (*Onobrychis viciifolia*). It was determined that sainfoin could compete with alfalfa in terms of protein and energy levels, was suitable for ruminant and monogastric species in terms of fiber content, and that condensed tannins reduced the risk of rumen bloat. Furthermore, it was reported that early-harvested sainfoin yielded higher protein and lower tannins, while late-harvested sainfoin yielded higher tannins and higher fiber.⁴⁴

While sainfoin can be grown alone, there are also studies where it is grown in combination with plants such as alfalfa. One study evaluated sainfoin in combination with alfalfa for several characteristics, including dry matter yield, canopy density, crude protein, NDF, ADF, and CT levels. Sainfoin-alfalfa mixtures yielded significant results, including unusually high yield, good quality, a low risk of bloat in ruminants, and improved plant viability. This demonstrates that sainfoin plays an important role in the nutritional system of ruminants.⁴⁵

Forage yield and forage quality being the crucial traits, sainfoin germplasm was evaluated in multiple years and wide variation was reported for fresh biomass as well as dry matter yield. Considering the three-year range, fresh forage yield range of (FFY) of 18.09- 37.70 t ha⁻¹ and dry matter yield (DMY) range of 4.74-13.5 tons ha⁻¹ were reported.⁴² For instance, a total annual forage yield of 10.79 tons ha⁻¹ DM was reported in the evaluation of 34 sainfoin populations under irrigation conditions in Iran.⁴⁶ A study made an evaluation for both seed yield and fodder production of the same trial and found a 3.2-ton ha⁻¹ DM yield in the first cut for forage in forage seed dual system management.⁴⁷

In addition to the management system, the planting also indicated to influence forage yield and a total DM yield of 7.3- and 6.2-tons ha⁻¹ was reported in spaced plant and sward conditions, respectively.⁴⁸ Mohajer et al. (2013) evaluated 72 sainfoin genotypes and obtained a total annual DM yield of 13.5 tons ha⁻¹.⁴⁹ Another study achieved a yield of 3.96 tons ha⁻¹ (DM) in Türkiye.⁵⁰ DM yield is a complex trait that is highly dependent on yield components and is highly influenced by genetic and environmental factors. For this reason, evaluating the genotypic potential of sainfoin in different environments is essential.

The sainfoin can be planted as a monoculture or in a mixture with other perennial grasses or alfalfa. The DM yield of sainfoin is reported to vary between 7-15 tons ha⁻¹ in Western Canada, depending on the different growing conditions.⁵¹ According to a five-year field study, sainfoin produced DM yields of more than 6 tons ha⁻¹ under rainfed conditions in Alberta, Canada.⁵² It was observed that the seed yield of Melrose sainfoin cultivar ranged between 307-1531 kg ha⁻¹ in the studies conducted in six different locations in Western Canada.^{52,53}

The sainfoin production area in Türkiye in the last five years is an average of 250.500 hectares. While sainfoin certified seed production fluctuates, the highest is reported to be about 750 tons in 2019 leaving a big gap that is probably filled with non-certified and non-registered seed. The amount of sainfoin seed production in the last five years is approximately 170 tons. While the sainfoin seed yield was 550 kg/ha in 2020, it was 400 kg/ha in 2021. The average yield over the last 5 years is 774 kg/ha.⁵⁴ Considering the aboveground fresh and dry biomass amounts of sainfoin in Türkiye, while the fresh biomass amount was approximately 1.93 million tons in 2020, the fresh biomass amount was approximately 1.55 million tons in 2021. The average amount of above-ground fresh biomass in the last five years is 1.8 million tons.⁵⁴

Environmental factors such as altitude, climate, and temperature changes were reported to have a significant impact on traits related to sainfoin forage yield.⁴¹ In addition to annual temperature changes, genotypic diversity has also been shown to have a significant impact on both forage yield and quality traits of sainfoin.⁴²

Seed yield and nutritional quality related traits

The nutritional properties of sainfoin seeds have gained attention earlier and several studies targeted understanding nutritional composition and usage of seeds in animal feeding. As one of the earliest studies, sainfoin seeds with and without hulls were added to a control diet for weaned piglets instead of using pea and soybean cake. Sainfoin seeds were found to provide an equally adequate source of amino acids when added to rations with a 10-16%. Thus, sainfoin seeds can be a valuable feed component for animals owing to the higher protein content.⁵⁵

Previous studies have revealed that sainfoin seeds can be considered as a new nutrition source for humans.^{22,30} Analyses of chemical composition of sainfoin seeds revealed that it contains 28.7% protein and 19.4% fiber, while the oil content did not exceed 8%. The total

amount of amino acids in the sainfoin seed powder was 26.94g/100g of product, and the ratio of indispensable amino acids was 37.85%. The limiting amino acid for the protein complex of sainfoin powder was tryptophan, with a ratio of 48.0%. Empirical studies indicated that sainfoin seed powder has a more balanced amino acid composition than wheat flour or peanuts. For this reason, sainfoin seeds can be considered a very promising food ingredient.³⁸

As a perennial crop sainfoin seed yield does not reach to its potential at the establishment yield and the seed production potential can be reached at the second year. However, in early sown, well fertilized and irrigated fields, seeds could be harvested in the sowing year. Seed yield is noted to be significant as it is reported to range 300-600 kg/ha of seeds in arid conditions. In optimum fields, the yield can exceed 1000 kg/ha.⁴⁰ In irrigated conditions, the yield have potential to reach up to 2000 kg/ha.⁴⁰ While the yield of sainfoin seed per hectare is reported to generally 500-900 kg of clean seeds, 1100 kg/ha yield was obtained in some sainfoin cultivars in Canada.^{35,51} While it is generally one seed harvest per growing season, it is reported to produce three to four seed crops per year in southern New Mexico, with sainfoin seed yields ranging from 56 to 1.344 kg/ha, averaging 336 kg/ha.⁵⁶ The sainfoin has not been specifically bred for the seed yield and the yield range reported in the above-mentioned studies is closer to some of the annual pulse crops and possesses a magnificent potential to be achieved in the breeding programs specifically targeting seed yield.

A comprehensive nutritional study was conducted to determine the potential of sainfoin seeds as a perennial legume for human consumption. The protein content of sainfoin seeds was found to range between 22 and 27%, and it was emphasized that they perform similarly to lentils and chickpeas, which hold a significant place in several cuisine cultures. Furthermore, it was reported that they contain high levels of unsaturated fatty acids (linoleic and oleic acid), have good fiber content, and contain higher levels of the minerals Fe and Zn than many legumes. It was also emphasized that the nutritional quality of sainfoin seeds is consistent across environments.⁵⁷

The study conducted to investigate the effects of a diet containing sainfoin seeds (*Onobrychis viciifolia* Scop.) on rats reported that diets containing sainfoin seeds at 5% and 10% were completely safe for rats. This highlights the potential use of sainfoin seeds as a food source for monogastric organisms, including humans.⁵⁸ The safety of sainfoin seeds were also investigated and its safety across many parameters, including heavy metals, mycotoxins, canavanine, and microbiological load was demonstrated.⁵⁹

Seed composition was also evaluated to determine the amino acid and fatty acid profiles of the sainfoin. This study found that its total protein content was approximately 24% and that it was rich in lysine, leucine, valine, and phenylalanine amino acids which are essential for human nutrition. Its total fat content was found to be 6-7%, and its low saturated fatty acid content is reported to be an advantage for human cardiovascular nutrition.¹⁸

The same research team also conducted a study to determine the processability and nutritional potential of sainfoin seed flour and reported that similarity to lentil and chickpea flours in terms of its high nutritional value and processability properties.⁶⁰ Another study on sainfoin seed flour investigated how fermentation of sainfoin seed flour with *S. boulardii* affected its nutritional value. This study examined the potential for sainfoin seed to be transformed into a functional food, its prebiotic potential, its antioxidant power, and the potential for reduced toxicity and anti-nutritional limitations. The study reported that sainfoin seed could be a new-generation nutritional source for human consumption, bakery products, protein bars, and even fermented beverages.⁶¹ Another study has demonstrated that sainfoin seeds have a significant potential to be used as an important food and plant protein source.⁶²

Conclusion

Sainfoin has very wide germplasm that manifests variation in terms of forage and seed yield and quality potential. The sainfoin hay has high potential in terms of both forage yield and forage quality and this variation can be effectively used to increase dry matter yield and enhance nutritional value of the sainfoin fodder. Therefore, evaluating and identifying germplasm that combine high yield and high quality or direct selection for the two traits would be essential breeding goals for future breeding efforts in sainfoin as a forage. Identifying candidate genotypes that provide stable performance in different environments and incorporating sainfoin into breeding systems would be another goal that could increase efficiency in animal production and make significant contributions to the development of sustainable feed resources.

The need for new plant based and sustainable protein sources for human nutrition is ever increasing, and sainfoin seeds have significant potential to meet this need. Sainfoin seeds can be developed for this purpose as they have clearly demonstrated to hold a significant potential in nutrition as well as robust safety profile. Sainfoin seed's high protein content, essential amino acid composition, rich fiber content, and abundance of unsaturated fatty acids indicate that this species can compete with traditional legumes such as lentils and chickpeas. Therefore, future studies focusing on the development of products obtained from sainfoin seeds, their inclusion in clinical nutrition studies, and food processing optimization by using functional food technologies will significantly evaluate this potential.

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